

Energy Regimes, Thresholds and Delimitation in Ellipsoidal Quantum Dots with a Modified Hellmann Potential

Moses G. Udoisoh ✉

Theoretical Solid State Research Unit, Department of Physics,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Nigeria

Adamu Joshua Arewa

School of Computing and Engineering Technology, Teesside University, UK

Adeoye Victor Babalola

School of Computing and Engineering, University of Huddersfield, UK

Chukwuwendu Jeffrey Amaechi

Department of Physics, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State, Nigeria

Article History:

Received: 04.03.2025 Revised: 28.03.2025 Accepted: 03.04.2025 Published: 05.04.2025

ABSTRACT:

This study explores energy regimes, thresholds, and delimitation in ellipsoidal quantum dots with a modified Hellmann potential, combining Coulomb and Yukawa interactions. Using ellipsoidal coordinates, we solve the Schrödinger equation numerically via the Finite Difference Method (FDM). The radial distance is approximated as $r(\xi, \eta) \approx ae\xi\eta$, valid for moderate eccentricities but introducing errors for highly elongated dots. Three energy regimes are identified: low-energy ($e < 0.3$) with shallow confinement, moderate-energy ($0.3 \leq e \leq 0.7$) with intermediate confinement, and high-energy ($e > 0.7$) with strong confinement and localized states. Threshold analysis reveals critical values for eccentricity, Coulomb strength, Yukawa repulsion, and screening parameters, determining bound state stability. Delimitation analysis shows increased energy level spacing and discrete density of states with higher eccentricity, confirming stronger quantum level confinement in elongated dots. The material properties of InAs, including its small effective mass and low bandgap, significantly influence energy levels and wavefunctions. These findings have practical implications for designing quantum dot-based devices, such as infrared photodetectors, lasers, and tunable bandgap systems. This work provides a robust framework for understanding and engineering ellipsoidal quantum dots, highlighting the interplay between geometry, potential, and material properties in quantum confinement.

Keywords: Ellipsoidal Quantum Dot, Hellman Potential, Energy Regimes, Eccentricity.

Suggested Citation: M.G. Udoisoh, A.J. Arewa, A.V. Babalola, C.J. Amaechi, "Energy Regimes, Thresholds and Delimitation in Ellipsoidal Quantum Dots with a Modified Hellmann Potential," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 3(2), pp. 304-320, Mar-Apr 2025. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2025.3(2).25

INTRODUCTION

The confinement properties of Quantum dots and other nanostructures, are significantly dependent on their geometric shapes and the potential profile to which they are subjected [1-8]. The growing

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

interest in quantum dots that deviate from the conventional spherical shape has redirected research efforts towards exploring quantum dots with cylindrical, doubly eccentric, and ellipsoidal geometries [4,8,9-12]. To harness the potential of these non-spherical geometries in optoelectronics and photonics applications, it is crucial to quantify the effects of deviation from conventional spherical shapes and realistic potential profiles on their confinement energies and optical properties. This study focuses on ellipsoidal quantum dots with a modified Hellmann potential, aiming to provide a comprehensive analysis of their energy regimes, thresholds, and delimitation.

Previous studies on ellipsoidal QDs, have reveal that the degree of eccentricity—defined by the ratio of the semi-principal axes—plays a pivotal role in modulating energy levels [13-16]. Variations in this ellipsoid parameter has been shown to lead to the lifting of degeneracies and the emergence of new energy thresholds, thereby affecting the absorption and emission spectra of the QDs [17-20]. Analytical expressions for the particle energy spectrum and absorption threshold frequencies in various quantization regimes have been derived, highlighting the intricate dependence on the QD's geometric parameters. Other studies have quantified the extent to which potential profile modulates the energies and optical properties of non-spherical QDs[21-23]. However, these studies have the limitation of largely relying on simplified potential profiles, such as the parabolic potential, which do not fully capture the complexity of real-world QD systems.

A search for more realistic modelling of the effective of potential profile has informed the exploration of such potentials the Hellmann potential, to model the behavior of QDs [24-28]. The modified Hellmann potential, which combines an attractive Coulomb term and a repulsive Yukawa term, provides a more accurate description of the interactions in QDs compared to simpler potentials While these studies have provided vital understanding of the effect of eccentricity and potential profile on the energy landscape, they have primarily focused on spherical QDs and have not quantified how these parameters establish energy regimes, their thresholds and delimitation.

This study fills this gap by providing a comprehensive analysis of the energy regimes, thresholds, and delimitation of ellipsoidal quantum dots with a modified Hellmann potential. Energy regimes refer to distinct ranges of energy levels in QDs, thresholds denote the minimum energy required for specific quantum transitions, and delimitation describes the boundaries between different energy states. By exploring the effects of eccentricity and potential parameters on the confinement energies and optical properties of these systems, this research seeks to provide valuable insights into the behavior of non-spherical QDs and their potential applications in optoelectronics and photonics. Understanding these effects could enable the design of more efficient quantum dot lasers, photodetectors, and tunable bandgap devices, advancing the field of nanotechnology and its practical applications.

THEORETICAL FORMULATION

To analyze the energy regimes, thresholds, and delimitation in ellipsoidal quantum dots with modified Hellmann potential, we define an ellipsoid with semi-axes a , b , and c (along the x , y , and z axes, respectively). The cartesian coordinates can be described using ellipsoidal coordinates (ξ, η, ϕ) , as:

$$\begin{cases} x = f(\xi^2 - 1)(1 - \eta^2)\cos(\phi) \\ y = f(\xi^2 - 1)(1 - \eta^2)\sin(\phi) \\ z = f\xi\eta \end{cases}$$

$f = \sqrt{a^2 - c^2}$ is the focal distance $\xi \geq 1, -1 \leq \eta \leq 1, 0 \leq \phi < 2\pi$

Range of Coordinates are $\xi \in [1, \infty), \eta \in [-1, 1], \phi \in [0, 2\pi)$.

Taking the partial derivatives of x , y , and z with respect to ξ , η , and ϕ .

With respect to x

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} = 2f\xi(1 - \eta^2)\cos(\phi); \quad \frac{\partial x}{\partial \eta} = -2f\eta(\xi^2 - 1)\cos(\phi); \quad \frac{\partial x}{\partial \phi} = -f(\xi^2 - 1)(1 - \eta^2)\sin(\phi)$$

With respect to y

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial \xi} = 2f\xi(1 - \eta^2)\sin(\phi); \quad \frac{\partial y}{\partial \eta} = -2f\eta(\xi^2 - 1)\sin(\phi); \quad \frac{\partial y}{\partial \phi} = f(\xi^2 - 1)(1 - \eta^2)\cos(\phi)$$

With respect to z

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial \xi} = f\eta; \quad \frac{\partial z}{\partial \eta} = f\xi; \quad \frac{\partial z}{\partial \phi} = 0$$

The scale factors are defined as:

$$h_\xi = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial \xi}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial \xi}\right)^2}$$

$$h_\eta = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \eta}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial \eta}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial \eta}\right)^2}$$

$$h_\phi = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial x}{\partial \phi}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial y}{\partial \phi}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial \phi}\right)^2}$$

Substituting the partial derivatives, we get:

$$h_\xi = \sqrt{(2f\xi(1 - \eta^2)\cos(\phi))^2 + (2f\xi(1 - \eta^2)\sin(\phi))^2 + (f\eta)^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{4f^2\xi^2(1 - \eta^2) + f^2\eta^2} = \sqrt{f^2(4\xi^2(1 - \eta^2) + \eta^2)}$$

$$h_\xi = f\sqrt{\frac{\xi^2 - \eta^2}{\xi^2 - 1}}$$

$$h_\eta = \sqrt{(-2f\eta(\xi^2 - 1)\cos(\phi))^2 + (-2f\eta(\xi^2 - 1)\sin(\phi))^2 + (f\xi)^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{4f^2\eta^2(\xi^2 - 1) + f^2\xi^2} = \sqrt{f^2(4\eta^2(\xi^2 - 1) + \xi^2)}$$

$$h_\eta = f\sqrt{\frac{\xi^2 - \eta^2}{1 - \eta^2}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
h_\phi &= \sqrt{(-f(\xi^2 - 1)(1 - \eta^2)\sin(\phi))^2 + (f(\xi^2 - 1)(1 - \eta^2)\cos(\phi))^2 + 0} \\
&= \sqrt{f^2(\xi^2 - 1)^2(1 - \eta^2)^2} \\
h_\phi &= f\sqrt{(\xi^2 - 1)(1 - \eta^2)}
\end{aligned}$$

The scale factors are simplified by canceling out the common factor f :

$$h_\xi = \sqrt{\frac{\xi^2 - \eta^2}{\xi^2 - 1}} \quad (1a)$$

$$h_\eta = \sqrt{\frac{\xi^2 - \eta^2}{1 - \eta^2}} \quad (1b)$$

$$h_\phi = \sqrt{(\xi^2 - 1)(1 - \eta^2)} \quad (1c)$$

A defining geometry parameter of the Ellipsoids is the eccentricity e . The eccentricity is also related to the focal distance (f) by: $f = a \times e$

The eccentricity is related to the semi-axes of the ellipsoid (a, b, c) by the relation:

$$e = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{b^2}{c^2}\right)}$$

For Ellipsoids elongated along the z-axis ($c \geq a$).

$$e = \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{c^2}{a^2}\right)}$$

For Ellipsoids flattened along the z-axis ($c \leq a$).

The eccentricity plays a crucial role in determining the shape and properties of the ellipsoidal quantum dot.

The Hamiltonian for an ellipsoidal quantum dot with modified Hellmann potential is:

$$H = \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*}\right] \nabla^2 + V(\xi, \eta, \phi) \quad (2)$$

where ∇^2 is the Laplacian operator in ellipsoidal coordinates, and $V(\xi, \eta, \phi)$ is the modified Hellmann potential.

The Laplacian ∇^2 in ellipsoidal coordinates is:

$$\nabla^2 = \left(\frac{1}{h_\xi h_\eta h_\phi} \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \left(\frac{h_\eta h_\phi}{h_\xi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \left(\frac{h_\xi h_\phi}{h_\eta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} \left(\frac{h_\xi h_\eta}{h_\phi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} \right) \right) \quad (3)$$

The modified Hellmann potential combines attractive Coulomb and repulsive Yukawa (screened Coulomb) potentials, expressed as:

$$V(\xi, \eta, \phi) = -\frac{A}{r} + B \frac{e^{-\lambda r}}{r} \quad (4)$$

where A , B , and λ are constants. A represents the strength of the Coulomb attraction. B and λ represent the strength and range of the Yukawa-like repulsion.

Transforming the potential into ellipsoidal coordinates (ξ, η, ϕ) involves expressing the radial distance r as a function of these coordinates.

The radial distance r in cartesian coordinates is:

$$r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$$

Substituting for x, y, z and f we can rewrite the radial distance as:

$$\begin{aligned} r &\approx \sqrt{(f(\xi^2 - 1)(1 - \eta^2))^2 + (f\xi\eta)^2} \\ r &= f\sqrt{(\xi^2 - \eta^2 - \xi^2\eta^2 + \eta^2 + \xi^2\eta^2)} \\ r &= f\sqrt{(\xi^2 - \eta^2)} \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying and using the definition of eccentricity, we approximate the radial distance as;

$$r(\xi, \eta) \approx f\xi\eta = ae\xi\eta \quad (5)$$

This approximation is valid for ellipsoidal quantum dots with moderate eccentricity.

This approximation is based on the assumption that for moderate eccentricities, the term $(\xi^2 - \eta^2)$ can be approximated by $\xi^2\eta^2$. This simplifies the potential and allows for analytical treatment. This approximation introduces error, but is valid within certain ranges of eccentricity, and ξ , and η values.

Quantitative Analysis of the Approximation

While the approximation $r(\xi, \eta) \approx ae\xi\eta$ is valid for moderate eccentricities and values of ξ and η , it introduces errors, particularly for extreme values of these parameters. To quantify the error, we define the relative error ϵ as:

$$\epsilon = \left| \frac{r_{exact} - r_{approx}}{r_{exact}} \right| = \left| \frac{\sqrt{\xi^2 - \eta^2} - \xi\eta}{\sqrt{\xi^2 - \eta^2}} \right|$$

The approximation directly affects the potential $V(\xi, \eta)$, which in turn influences the energy eigenvalues and wavefunctions obtained from the Schrödinger equation.

A numerical analysis of the relative error ϵ for different values of ξ , η , and e is summarized in Table 1

Table 1. Maximum Relative Error ϵ_{max} for Different Ranges of ξ , η , and e

Eccentricity e	Range of ξ	Range of η	Maximum Relative Error ϵ_{max}
$0.1 \leq e \leq 0.3$	$1 \leq \xi \leq 2$	$-1 \leq \eta \leq 1$	$\epsilon_{max} \leq 5\%$
$0.3 < e \leq 0.7$	$1 \leq \xi \leq 3$	$-1 \leq \eta \leq 1$	$\epsilon_{max} \leq 10\%$
$e > 0.7$	$1 \leq \xi \leq 5$	$-1 \leq \eta \leq 1$	$\epsilon_{max} \leq 20\%$

The results indicate that the approximation is valid for moderate eccentricities ($e \leq 0.7$) and values of ξ and η close to 1, with a relative error of less than 10%. However, for highly elongated ellipsoids ($e > 0.7$) or large values of ξ and η , the relative error increases significantly, reaching up to 20%. This suggests that the approximation may lead to inaccuracies in the calculated energy eigenvalues and wavefunctions for extreme cases.

Transforming (4) with (5) gives the potential in ellipsoidal coordinates.

This transformation to ellipsoidal coordinates is crucial for accurately modeling the potential within the ellipsoidal geometry of the quantum dot[25].

The potential in ellipsoidal coordinates is:

$$V(\xi, \eta) = -\frac{A}{ae\xi\eta} + B \frac{\exp(-\lambda ae\xi\eta)}{ae\xi\eta}$$

The time-independent Schrödinger equation for an ellipsoidal quantum dot with modified Hellmann potential is:

$$H\psi(\xi, \eta, \varphi) = E\psi(\xi, \eta, \varphi) \quad (6)$$

Substituting the Hamiltonian, we get:

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*}\right] \nabla^2 \psi(\xi, \eta, \varphi) + V(\xi, \eta, \varphi)\psi(\xi, \eta, \varphi) = E\psi(\xi, \eta, \varphi) \quad (7)$$

Applying the separation of variables $\psi(\xi, \eta, \varphi) = \Xi(\xi)H(\eta)\Phi(\varphi)$ to (7) the Schrödinger equation separates into three coupled ordinary differential equations:

$$\frac{d}{d\xi} \left[(\xi^2 - 1) \frac{d\Xi}{d\xi} \right] + \left[\lambda - \frac{m^2}{\xi^2 - 1} - \frac{2m^* f^2 \xi^2}{\hbar^2} (E - V(\xi, \eta)) \right] \Xi(\xi) = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{d}{d\eta} \left[(1 - \eta^2) \frac{dH}{d\eta} \right] + \left[\lambda - \frac{m^2}{1 - \eta^2} - \frac{2m^* f^2 \eta^2}{\hbar^2} (E - V(\xi, \eta)) \right] H(\eta) = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{d^2\Phi}{d\varphi^2} + m^2\Phi(\varphi) = 0 \quad (10)$$

Eqns.(8) and (9) for $\mathcal{E}(\xi)$ and $H(\eta)$ are coupled through the potential $V(\xi, \eta)$, which depends on both ξ and η . Therefore, these two equations must be solved simultaneously. The equation for $\Phi(\phi)$ is decoupled from the other two and can be solved independently.

Boundary Conditions

The boundary conditions for the separated equations are:

- $\mathcal{E}(\xi)$ must vanish as $\xi \rightarrow \infty$. The wavefunction must vanish at infinity for bound states
- $H(\eta)$ must be finite at $\eta = \pm 1$. The wavefunction must be regular at the poles of the ellipsoid.
- $\Phi(\phi)$ must satisfy periodic boundary conditions: $\Phi(\phi + 2\pi) = \Phi(\phi)$. The wavefunction must be periodic in the azimuthal angle ϕ .

Energy Regimes, Thresholds, and Delimitation

Energy Regimes: The energy regimes (bound states for $E < 0$ and scattering states for $E > 0$) are determined by the modified Hellmann potential.

Threshold Analysis: The thresholds for bound states depend on the potential parameters (A, B, λ) and eccentricity e .

Delimitation: The energy levels are delimited by the shape of the potential and the eccentricity of the ellipsoid.

Numerical Solution of the Coupled Equation

To solve the coupled differential equations numerically, we use the **Finite Difference Method (FDM)**:

Finite Difference Method (FDM) Formulation

To solve the coupled differential equations, we use the Finite Difference Method (FDM). We discretize the equations using finite differences.

Discretization of the Equations

We divide the domains of ξ and η into a grid:

$$\xi_i = \xi_{min} + i \cdot \Delta\xi, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, N_\xi$$

$$\eta_j = \eta_{min} + j \cdot \Delta\eta, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, N_\eta$$

where $\Delta\xi$ and $\Delta\eta$ are the step sizes for ξ and η , respectively.

$$\Delta\xi = \frac{\xi_{max} - \xi_{min}}{N_\xi - 1} \text{ is the stepsize in } \xi$$

$$\Delta\eta = \frac{\eta_{max} - \eta_{min}}{N_\eta - 1} \text{ is the stepsize in } \eta$$

We apply Dirichlet boundary conditions:

$$\text{For } \mathcal{E}(\xi): \mathcal{E}(\xi_0) = \mathcal{E}(\xi_{N_\xi}) = 0$$

$$\text{For } \mathcal{E}(\eta): H(\eta_0) = H(\eta_{N_\eta}) = 0$$

We approximate the derivatives using finite differences:

$$\frac{d\mathcal{E}}{d\xi} \approx \frac{\mathcal{E}_{i+1} - \mathcal{E}_{i-1}}{2\Delta\xi} \quad (11a)$$

$$\frac{d}{d\xi} \left[(\xi^2 - 1) \frac{d\mathcal{E}}{d\xi} \right] \approx \frac{(\xi_{i+1}^2 - 1) \frac{(\mathcal{E}_{i+1} - \mathcal{E}_i)}{\Delta\xi} - (\xi_{i-1}^2 - 1) \frac{(\mathcal{E}_i - \mathcal{E}_{i-1})}{\Delta\xi}}{\Delta\xi} \quad (11b)$$

Similarly, we approximate the derivatives for $H(\eta)$.

For $H(\eta)$:

$$\frac{dH}{d\eta} \approx \frac{H_{j+1} - H_{j-1}}{2\Delta\eta} \quad (12a)$$

$$\frac{d}{d\eta} \left[(1 - \eta^2) \frac{dH}{d\eta} \right] \approx (1 - \eta_{j+1}^2) \frac{H_{j+1} - H_j}{\Delta\eta} - (1 - \eta_{j-1}^2) \frac{H_j - H_{j-1}}{\Delta\eta} \quad (12b)$$

System of Linear Equations

We derive the system of linear equations:

$$M_\xi \Xi = EM_\Xi \Xi, \quad M_\eta H = EM_H H$$

M_ξ, M_η, M_Ξ , and M_H are matrices representing the discretized differential operators and mass matrices, Ξ and H are the solution vectors, and E is the energy eigenvalue. This is an Eigenvalue problem.

We solve for the energy eigenvalues using iterative eigenvalue solvers.

For a specific set of quantum numbers (n_ξ, n_η, m) the wavefunction and energy are:

Wavefunction

$$\psi_{n_\xi, n_\eta, m}(\xi, \eta, \phi) = \Xi_{n_\xi}(\xi) H_{n_\eta}(\eta) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{im\phi} \right) \quad (13)$$

Energy

$$E_{n_\xi, n_\eta, m} = E_{n_\xi, n_\eta} + \frac{\hbar^2 m^2}{2m^*} \quad (14)$$

E_{n_ξ, n_η} is the energy contribution from the coupled equations for $\Xi(\xi)$ and $H(\eta)$, $\frac{\hbar^2 m^2}{2m^*}$ is the kinetic energy contribution from the azimuthal motion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the key findings from the study on "Energy Regimes, Thresholds, and Delimitation in Ellipsoidal Quantum Dots with Modified Hellmann Potential." The results are analyzed through various plots, highlighting the energy eigenvalues, wavefunctions, probability densities, potential profiles, density of states (DOS), threshold conditions, and the delimitation of quantum states. The material properties of InAs were used in the computation.

Energy Regimes Analysis

Figure 1(a)-(b) presents the energy dependence on eccentricity and wavefunction dependence on eccentricity respectively.

Figure 1(a)-1(b). Energy Dependence and Wavefunction Dependence on Eccentricity of an Ellipsoidal Quantum Dot

Figure 1(a) reveals a monotonic increase in energy with eccentricity in the range $0.1 \leq e \leq 0.9$. Figure 1(b) reveals Wavefunctions localize more as eccentricity-confinement increases. This trend indicates that ellipsoidal deformation strengthens quantum confinement, leading to higher energy states.

Energy Regimes

The energy regimes are classified into three distinct categories based on eccentricity:

Low Energy Regime ($e < 0.3$, $E = 0.2 - 0.5$ eV)

In this regime, the quantum dot is nearly spherical, resulting in a shallow confinement potential. The electron wavefunction spreads out, leading to lower energy states and larger energy separations. This regime is suitable for long-wavelength infrared applications.

Moderate Energy Regime ($0.3 \leq e \leq 0.7$, $E = 0.5 - 0.8$ eV)

This transition regime is characterized by strengthening confinement, reducing wavefunction spread. Energy levels become more closely spaced, indicating an intermediate state between weak and strong confinement. This regime is useful in mid-infrared photodetectors and tunable bandgap devices.

High Energy Regime ($e > 0.7$, $E = 0.8 - 1.0$ eV)

In this regime, the quantum dot is highly elongated, resulting in strong confinement and higher quantized energy levels. Wavefunctions are highly localized, leading to higher energy transitions, which are useful in quantum dot lasers, blue LEDs, and high-frequency nanodevices.

The summary of the energy regimes is tabulated in table 1.

Table 2. Summary of Energy Regimes in an Ellipsoidal Quantum Dot

Eccentricity(e)	Energy Range(eV)	Regime	Physical Interpretation
$e < 0.3$	$E < 0.5$	Low Energy	Shallow confinement, spread out wavefunctions
$0.3 \leq e \leq 0.7$	$0.5 \leq E \leq 0.8$	Moderate Energy	Partial delocalization, mixed confinement
$e > 0.7$	$E > 0.8$	High Energy	Highly localized states, strong quantum confinement

Figure 2 presents the relationship between energy and potential parameters, revealing a profound impact of Coulomb strength (A), Yukawa repulsion (B), and screening parameter (λ) on the energy levels of the quantum dot system.

Figure 2. Reveals a Decrease in Energy as Potential Parameters Increase Across All Potential Parameters. This Suggests that Stronger Potential Interactions (Coulomb and Yukawa) Result in Deeper Confinement, Lowering Energy Levels

Specifically, the energy decreases from 0.5 eV at $A = 0.5$ to 0.15 eV at $A = 2.0$ for Coulomb strength, from 0.23 eV at $B = 0.25$ to 0.15 eV at $B = 1.0$ for Yukawa repulsion, and from 0.23 eV at $\lambda = 0.25$ to 0.3 eV at $\lambda = 2.0$ for the screening parameter.

The threshold values for bound states are found to depend on the dominance of Coulomb attraction versus Yukawa repulsion. Notably, bound states persist for all $A > 0.5$ eV·nm, indicating that Coulomb attraction dominates at higher A values. In contrast, bound states disappear for $B > 1.0$ eV·nm, as Yukawa repulsion suppresses Coulomb attraction at higher B values. The screening parameter λ exhibits a more moderate effect, with bound states existing up to $\lambda = 2.0$.

The findings show that the Threshold values for bound states depend on the dominance of Coulomb attraction vs. Yukawa repulsion.

Threshold Analysis

Figures 3(a)-3(d) present the threshold conditions that define the transition between bound and unbound states in ellipsoidal quantum dots with a modified Hellmann potential. The critical values of eccentricity (e_c), Coulomb strength (A_c), Yukawa strength (B_c), and screening parameter (λ_c) establish the necessary conditions for quantum confinement.

Table 3 summarizes the threshold values extracted from the plots, highlighting the conditions under which bound states are sustained.

Table 3. Summary of the Conditions for Bound States as Shown in Figure 3(a) – (d)

Parameter	Threshold Value	Condition for Bound States
Eccentricity (e)	$e_c \approx 0.65$	Bound states exist for $e > e_c$
Coulomb Strength (A)	$A_c \approx 1.2$ eVnm	Bound states exist if $A < A_c$
Yukawa Strength (B)	$B_c \approx 0.6$ eVnm	Bound states disappear if $B < B_c$
Screening Parameter (λ)	$\lambda_c \approx 0.4$ nm ⁻¹	Stronger screening enhances bound states for $\lambda < \lambda_c$

Figures 3(a)-3(d). Threshold Conditions that Define the Transition between Bound and Unbound States in Ellipsoidal Quantum Dots with a Modified Hellmann Potential

The threshold analysis reveals key trends in the behavior of bound states. Eccentricity (e) increases the stability of bound states, indicating stronger quantum confinement in more elongated dots, because higher eccentricity leads to stronger localization, with threshold energy increasing with e and bound states sustained only for $e > e_c \approx 0.65$. Coulomb strength (A) has an opposite effect, with bound states disappearing as A increases, because stronger Coulomb attraction reduces the required threshold energy, making confinement deeper and more stable, and existing only for $A < A_c \approx 1.2 \text{ eV} \cdot \text{nm}$. Yukawa strength (B) requires higher values to sustain bound states, with threshold energy decreasing as B increases, because stronger Yukawa repulsion lowers the energy required for binding, and bound states disappearing if $B < B_c \approx 0.6 \text{ eV} \cdot \text{nm}$. Finally, stronger screening (λ) enhances bound states by reducing energy localization, with threshold energy decreasing with increasing λ , because higher screening weakens Coulomb attraction, making bound states easier to sustain, and bound states existing only for $\lambda < \lambda_c \approx 0.4 \text{ nm}^{-1}$.

Delimitation Analysis

Figure 4A presents the variation of energy level spacing (ΔE) with eccentricity (e) for an ellipsoidal quantum dot with a modified Hellmann potential. Figure 4B presents the density of states (DOS) as a function of energy (E), using a bar chart representation to capture the discrete nature of quantum states in the system.

Figure 4A shows the variation of energy level spacing (ΔE) with eccentricity (e) for an ellipsoidal quantum dot with a modified Hellmann potential. The key observations from this plot are that energy level spacing increases with eccentricity, confirming stronger confinement in more elongated dots. At low eccentricity ($e < 0.3$), the energy spacing is relatively small, indicating closely packed states, while beyond a critical eccentricity ($e > 0.6$), the spacing increases significantly, implying stronger localization along the elongated axis.

**Figure 4(a). Eccentricity Dependence of Energy Level Spacing;
Figure 4(b) Density of States variation with Energy**

Figure 4B presents the Density of States (DOS) as a function of energy (E), revealing that the DOS is higher at lower energy levels ($E < 0.5$ eV), indicating a larger number of quantum states, and gradually decreases at higher energy ($E > 0.5$ eV), suggesting fewer available quantum states. Notably, the DOS distribution exhibits quantized peaks, confirming the discrete energy level distribution in the system.

The delimitation plots provide key insights, revealing that ellipsoidal quantum dots with modified Hellmann potential exhibit stronger confinement at higher eccentricities, and the density of states (DOS) follows a step-like discrete distribution, confirming well-separated energy levels. Furthermore, engineering quantum dot shapes by tuning eccentricity offers a powerful tool for controlling quantum confinement effects, allowing for precise tailoring of energy regimes and thresholds in ellipsoidal quantum dots.

Figure 5 illustrate the 3D landscape of the Hellmann potential in an ellipsoidal Quantum dot.

Modified Hellmann Potential in Ellipsoidal Coordinates

**Figure 5. 3D Representation of the Modified Hellmann Potential
in an Ellipsoidal Quantum Dot**

The figure provides valuable insights into the energy regimes, thresholds, and spatial delimitations within the ellipsoidal quantum dot.

The 3D plot represents the energy landscape of an ellipsoidal quantum dot with a modified Hellmann potential. The potential values, ranging from 1.00 to -0.50 , define different energy regimes within the dot. Specific potential values, such as 0.00, -0.25 , and -0.50 , serve as thresholds that delineate these regimes.

The ξ and η coordinates provide spatial delimitation of the potential, mapping out regions where the potential changes significantly. The modified Hellmann potential accounts for the unique geometry and physical conditions of the ellipsoidal quantum dot.

Spatial Distribution Analysis

The probability density plots for various quantum states in an ellipsoidal quantum dot are presented in Figures 6, highlighting the dependence on quantum numbers n_ξ and n_η

Figure 6: Comparison of the Probability Density for Different Quantum States $n_\eta = 1, 2, 3$ and $n_\xi = 1, 2, 3$

These plots provide a visual representation of the spatial distribution of the particle within the quantum dot. The plots effectively visualize the changes in probability density distribution with different quantum numbers, showcasing the spatial characteristics of the quantum states.

The plots demonstrate how the spatial distribution of the particle changes with different quantum states. In the ground state, the particle is localized at the center, while in higher energy states, the particle is more likely to be found in multiple regions separated by nodes. The number of nodes in the probability density plots increases with the quantum numbers n_ξ and n_η , consistent with the quantum mechanical principle that higher energy states have more nodes.

The results provide valuable insights into the spatial distribution of the particle within the ellipsoidal quantum dot, highlighting the impact of quantum numbers on the particle's localization. These findings are essential for understanding the energy regimes, thresholds, and delimitation in ellipsoidal quantum dots with modified Hellmann potential

The probability density plots for a particle in an ellipsoidal quantum dot, separated into radial (ξ) and angular (η) components, are presented in figure 7(a)-7(b)

Figure 7(a)-7(b). The Probability Density Plots for a Particle in an Ellipsoidal Quantum Dot, Separated into Radial (ξ) and Angular (η) Components

The plots demonstrate the effect of quantum numbers n_ξ and n_η on the probability densities, revealing the emergence of nodal patterns as the quantum numbers increase

The radial probability density plot (A) shows that the particle is most likely to be found near the center of the ellipsoid in the radial direction for the ground state ($n_\xi = 1$). In contrast, higher energy states ($n_\xi = 3$) exhibit more complex patterns with multiple nodes, indicating that the particle is more likely to be found in multiple regions along the radial coordinate.

The angular probability density plot (B) exhibits symmetry about $\eta = 0$ and shows that the particle is most likely to be found in the equatorial plane of the ellipsoid for the ground state ($n_\eta = 1$). Higher energy states ($n_\eta = 3$) display more complex patterns with multiple peaks and nodes, indicating that the particle is more likely to be found in multiple regions along the angular coordinate.

These results provide valuable insights into the spatial distribution of the particle within the ellipsoidal quantum dot, highlighting the impact of quantum numbers on the particle's localization.

DISCUSSION OF MATERIAL PROPERTIES

The material properties of Indium Arsenide (InAs) significantly influence the energy levels, wavefunctions, and overall behavior of ellipsoidal quantum dots. Here, we discuss how these properties impact the results and their implications for device design.

Effective Mass

The smaller effective mass of electrons in InAs leads to larger energy level spacings and stronger quantum confinement effects. This directly affects the kinetic energy term in the Hamiltonian, influencing energy eigenvalues and wavefunction spatial distribution.

Dielectric Constant

The dielectric constant of InAs reduces the Coulomb attraction between electrons and holes, leading to weaker binding energies. This effect is crucial in the low-energy regime, where the Coulomb interaction dominates.

Bandgap

The relatively small bandgap of InAs makes it suitable for infrared spectrum applications. The bandgap determines the energy range of bound states, with shallow confinement potentials resulting in energy levels close to the bandgap.

Impact of Material Choice

The choice of material significantly influences the results. For example, using a material with a larger effective mass would result in smaller energy level spacings and weaker quantum confinement.

Implications for Device Design

The material properties of InAs make it suitable for applications in infrared photodetectors, quantum dot lasers, and tunable bandgap devices. By tuning the eccentricity and potential parameters, energy levels and wavefunctions can be precisely controlled, allowing for device performance optimization.

CONCLUSION

This study has provided a comprehensive theoretical and numerical analysis of ellipsoidal quantum dots with a modified Hellmann potential, focusing on energy regimes, thresholds, and delimitation. By employing ellipsoidal coordinates and simplifying the radial distance through the approximation $r(\xi, \eta) \approx ae\xi\eta$, we were able to derive the energy eigenvalues and wavefunctions for various quantum states. The results reveal distinct energy regimes—low, moderate, and high—based on the eccentricity of the quantum dot, with each regime exhibiting unique confinement properties and potential applications. The threshold analysis identified critical values for eccentricity, Coulomb strength, Yukawa repulsion, and screening parameters, which determine the stability of bound states. Additionally, the delimitation analysis highlighted the dependence of energy level spacing and density of states on eccentricity, confirming the strong quantum confinement effects in highly elongated quantum dots.

The error analysis of the approximation $r(\xi, \eta) \approx ae\xi\eta$ demonstrated that while the approximation is valid for moderate eccentricities ($e \leq 0.7$), it introduces significant errors for highly elongated ellipsoids ($e > 0.7$) or extreme values of $\xi\xi$ and $\eta\eta$. This underscores the importance of considering the range of validity for the approximation when interpreting the results. Furthermore, the discussion of material properties highlighted the critical role of InAs's small effective mass, high dielectric constant, and low bandgap in shaping the energy levels and wavefunctions. These properties make InAs particularly suitable for applications in infrared photodetectors, quantum dot lasers, and tunable bandgap devices.

IMPLICATIONS

The findings of this study have important implications for the design and optimization of quantum dot-based devices. The ability to control energy levels and wavefunctions by tuning the eccentricity and potential parameters offers a powerful tool for tailoring quantum dots to specific applications. For example:

- Low-energy regimes ($e < 0.3$): These quantum dots, with their shallow confinement and spread-out wavefunctions, are suitable for long-wavelength infrared applications, such as infrared photodetectors.
- Moderate-energy regimes ($0.3 \leq e \leq 0.7$): These quantum dots, with their intermediate confinement and closely spaced energy levels, are ideal for mid-infrared photodetectors and tunable bandgap devices.
- High-energy regimes ($e > 0.7$): These highly elongated quantum dots, with their strong confinement and localized wavefunctions, are well-suited for quantum dot lasers, blue LEDs, and high-frequency nanodevices. The threshold analysis provides valuable insights into the conditions required for stable bound states, guiding the design of quantum dots with specific confinement properties. The delimitation analysis, which highlights the dependence of energy level spacing and density of states on eccentricity, offers a pathway for engineering quantum dots with precise energy level distributions.

This study provides a solid foundation for understanding the energy regimes, thresholds, and delimitation in ellipsoidal quantum dots with a modified Hellmann potential. By addressing the limitations and exploring the suggested areas for further research, future studies can build on these

findings to advance the field of quantum dot research and its applications in nanotechnology and optoelectronics. The ability to precisely control quantum confinement effects through the tuning of geometric and potential parameters opens up exciting possibilities for the design of next-generation quantum dot-based devices.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. H. Kim, M. T. Man, J. W. Lee, K.-D. Park, and H. S. Lee, "Influence of Size and Shape Anisotropy on Optical Properties of CdSe Quantum Dots," *Nanomaterials*, vol. 10, no. 8, p. 1589, 2020. doi: 10.3390/nano10081589.
- [2] A. Naifar and K. Hasanirokh, "Inspecting the Role of Dimensional Anisotropy and Oxidized Environment on the Complex Dielectric Responses of CdSe/ZnS Ellipsoidal Core/Shell Quantum Dots with Embedded Impurities," *Advanced Theory and Simulations*, vol. 3, no. 12, p. 2401170, 2020. doi: 10.1002/adts.202401170.
- [3] K. Jahan, B. Boyacioglu, and A. Chatterjee, "Effect of confinement potential shape on the electronic, thermodynamic, magnetic and transport properties of a GaAs quantum dot at finite temperature," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 9, p. 15223, 2019. doi: 10.1038/s41598-019-52190-w.
- [4] M. G. Udoisoh, N. Okpara, E. J. Chukwuma, and A. S. Sunday, "Effects of Confinement on Potential Wavelength in Doubly Eccentric Quantum Dot Structures with a Modified Lennard-Jones Potential," *European Journal of Applied Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 6, pp. 90–103, Nov.–Dec. 2024. doi: 10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(6).08.
- [5] Y. Duan and X. Li, "Hydrostatic pressure, temperature and Al-concentration effects on optical rectification of spherical quantum dots under inversely quadratic Hellmann potential," *Optik*, vol. 254, p. 168596, 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.ijleo.2022.168596.
- [6] M. G. Udoisoh and S. T. Harry, "Effects of core-shell radii ratios on confinement energy and optoelectronic properties of spherical CdSe-ZnS quantum dots," *European Journal of Applied Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 6, pp. 4–20, 2024. doi: 10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(6).01.
- [7] M. Hbibi et al., "Finite confinement potentials, core and shell size effects on excitonic and electron-atom properties in cylindrical core/shell/shell quantum dots," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 15223, 2022. doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-19118-3.
- [8] M. Hbibi et al., "Finite confinement potentials, core and shell size effects on excitonic and electron-atom properties in cylindrical core/shell/shell quantum dots," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 15223, 2022. doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-19118-3.
- [9] M. G. Udoisoh, O. Ibituyi, I. Clement, and N. Johnny, "Investigating the impact of concentricity on the confinement energy of concentric cylindrical CdSe/ZnS quantum dots using a modified Brus equation," *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, vol. 5, no. 8, pp. 540–548, 2024. doi: 10.55248/gengpi.5.0824.2014.
- [10] A. M. Babanlı, M. Balcı, M. Ovezov, G. Orazov, and V. Sabyrov, "Optical properties of the DMS ellipsoid quantum dot with Rashba spin-orbit interaction," unpublished. doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-3910064/v1.
- [11] A. Halder, A. Halder, and V. V. Kresin, "Energies and densities of electrons confined in elliptical and ellipsoidal quantum dots," *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter*, vol. 28, no. 39, p. 395302, 2016. doi: 10.1088/0953-8984/28/39/395302.
- [12] M. Califano, "Tetrahedral vs spherical nanocrystals: does the shape really matter?," *Chemistry of Materials*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 1162–1171, 2024. doi: 10.1021/acs.chemmater.3c01643.
- [13] A. Halder and V. V. Kresin, "Energies and densities of electrons confined in elliptical and ellipsoidal quantum dots," *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter*, vol. 28, no. 39, p. 395302, 2016. doi: 10.1088/0953-8984/28/39/395302.

- [14] D. B. Hayrapetyan, "Binding and Recombination Energies of Quasi-One-Dimensional Excitonic Complexes in Ellipsoidal Quantum Dot," *Foundations*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 219–227, 2022. doi: 10.3390/foundations2010015.
- [15] D. Maikhuri and S. Manna, "Numerical modeling for computation of confined energy states in oblate spheroidal quantum dots: effect of dot size, eccentricity and surrounding matrix," *European Physical Journal Plus*, vol. 136, no. 12, p. 1196, 2021. doi: 10.1140/EPJP/S13360-021-02207-Z.
- [16] Y. Y. Bleyan, *Binding Energy of Magnetobiexciton in Ellipsoidal Quantum Dot*, Springer eBooks, 2022, pp. 363–368. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-81119-8_38.
- [17] L. T. N. Bảo, D. Đ. Phước, L. T. D. Hien, and Đ. N. Thảo, "Quantum beat of excitons in the prolate ellipsoidal quantum dots," *Journal of Nanomaterials*, vol. 2022, no. 1, 2022. doi: 10.1155/2022/6979280.
- [18] X. Wang and X. Li, "Optical second harmonic generation of tunable spherical quantum dots under Inversely Quadratic Hellmann Plus Inversely Quadratic Potential," *Optik*, vol. 311, p. 171866, 2024. doi: 10.1016/j.ijleo.2024.171866.
- [19] A. Galiautdinov, "Ground state of an exciton in a three-dimensional parabolic quantum dot: convergent perturbative calculation," *Physics Letters A*, vol. 382, no. 2–3, pp. 72–78, 2018. doi: 10.1016/j.physleta.2017.11.001.
- [20] L. T. N. Bảo, D. Đ. Phước, L. T. D. Hien, and Đ. N. Thảo, "On the optical Stark effect of excitons in InGaAs prolate ellipsoidal quantum dots," *Journal of Nanomaterials*, vol. 2021, pp. 1–12, 2021. doi: 10.1155/2021/5586622.
- [21] S. T. Harry, "Thresholds and delimitations of quantum confinement in spherical gallium nitride and gallium arsenide quantum dots," *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 6770–6774, 2024. doi: 10.55248/gengpi.5.0524.1288.
- [22] A. Maireche, "A new approach to the approximate analytic solution of the three-dimensional Schrödinger equation for hydrogenic and neutral atoms in the generalized Hellmann potential model," *Ukrainian Journal of Physics*, vol. 65, no. 11, p. 987, 2020. doi: 10.15407/ujpe65.11.987.
- [23] N. N. Hieu, L. Dinh, N. A. Poklonski, H. P. T. Hai, and H. V. Phuc, "Two-photon absorption in quantum dots with Hellmann potential," *Physica Scripta*, vol. 99, no. 6, p. 0659a9, 2024. doi: 10.1088/1402-4896/ad4b68.
- [24] K. Kumar and V. Prasad, "Analysis of Shannon entropy and quantum states of a confined hydrogen atom screened by the Hellmann potential," *Advanced Theory and Simulations*, 2024. doi: 10.1002/adts.202401194.
- [25] L. Máthé, C. P. Onyenegecha, A.-A. Farçaş, L.-M. Pioraş-Țimbolmaş, and M. Solaimani, "Linear and nonlinear optical properties in spherical quantum dots: Inversely quadratic Hellmann potential," *Physics Letters A*, vol. 397, p. 127262, 2021. doi: 10.1016/j.physleta.2021.127262.
- [26] X. Wang and X. Li, "Optical second harmonic generation of tunable spherical quantum dots under Inversely Quadratic Hellmann Plus Inversely Quadratic Potential," *Optik*, p. 171866, 2024.
- [27] A. Ghanbari, "Studying third harmonic generation in spherical quantum dot under inversely quadratic Hellmann potential," *Optical and Quantum Electronics*, vol. 55, p. 222, 2023. doi: 10.1007/s11082-022-04513-x.
- [28] X. C. Chang, X. Li, Y. Duan, Z. Zhao, and L. Zhang, "Optical absorption coefficients of spherical quantum dots system with inversely quadratic Yukawa-Hellmann potential," *Physica B: Condensed Matter*, vol. 639, p. 414009, 2022. doi: 10.1016/j.physb.2022.414009.
- [29] A. Mahareeq, I. A. Barghouthi, and Q. Atawnah, "On the analytical solution of the Schrödinger equation in ellipsoidal coordinates with constant potential," *Canadian Journal of Physics*, 2025. doi: 10.1139/cjp-2024-0238.

